

STUDIES ON LIPASE FROM OIL SEEDS. PART XVI. EFFECT
OF SOME WATER-SOLUBLE VITAMINS ON THE ACTIVITY
OF RICINUS LIPASE FROM CASTOR SEEDS

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Effect of addition of ascorbic acid, thiamine hydrochloride and riboflavin on the enzymic hydrolysis of groundnut oil has been investigated.

Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 6) have studied the general properties of ricinus lipase from castor seed. Ramakrishnan and Banerjee (under publication in *Science*) found that lipase obtained from some molds grown on oil seeds has got better activity than that obtained from the oil seeds. They are investigating the mold lipase in detail with a view to preparing it on a large scale. Ramakrishnan and Srinivasan (*Science & Culture*, 1951, 16, 320) found that these lipolytic molds also synthesised water-soluble vitamins like ascorbic acid, riboflavin, thiamine hydrochloride, etc. Hence it will be appropriate to investigate how the vitamins in the molds affect the activity of the lipase. So the preliminary investigation was carried out to study the effect of added vitamins on the activity of ricinus lipase from castor seed which would give an idea of the relation between these vitamins and the lipase activity.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The lipase powder was prepared from fresh, well ripened castor seeds by Longnecker and Haly's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2019). The hydrolysis of freshly prepared groundnut oil was carried out using the lipase powder, disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer and different water-soluble vitamins.

In the first investigation, each set of the experiments consisted of groundnut oil (1 c.c.), water (5 c.c.), 10 mg. of water-soluble vitamins (Eli Lilly products), lipase (0.1 g.) and 2 c.c. of disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer mixture of varying p_H value and a few drops of toluene in a conical flask. It was corked well and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. The hydrolysis of the oil was also carried out using lipase only without vitamins. Always a blank accompanied each sample. Necessary precautions were taken to note readings under sterile conditions. After the period of incubation, each flask was taken out and the contents titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide. The difference between the sample and the blank gave the activity of the lipase in terms of c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

pH .	Diff. in c. c. of $N/10$ -NaOH bet. the sample and the blank in sample containing			
	Thiamine.	Ascorbic acid.	Riboflavin.	Lipase only.
3.6	9.7	15.8	10.2	6.3
4.8	13.8	24.1	15.6	12.2
5.2	10.5	18.9	12.8	7.8
5.5	9.8	14.2	11.3	6.4
5.7	7.5	11.8	9.9	5.3
6.2	6.8	9.6	7.3	4.2
7.2	6.2	8.2	6.9	3.3
7.6	5.5	6.1	5.8	2.7

In the second investigation, the hydrolysis of groundnut oil was carried out using castor seed lipase, disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer mixture of pH 4.8 and different amounts of vitamins. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Amount of vitamin added.	Diff. in c. c. of $N/10$ -NaOH bet. the sample and the blank in sample containing			
	Thiamine.	Ascorbic acid.	Riboflavin	Lipase only.
10 mg.	13.8	24.1	15.6	12.2
20	14.9	28.1	15.7	12.2
40	15.2	28.1	15.7	12.2
60	14.2	28.3	14.8	12.2

DISCUSSION

From Table I, it is found that the optimum pH for the activity of the ricinus lipase does not change by the addition of vitamins as the activity is maximum in all cases at 4.8 pH . The activity of the lipase is enhanced by the addition of vitamins and it ascends in the order: thiamine, riboflavin and ascorbic acid.

From Table II, it is found that as the concentration of the added vitamins increases, the activity of the lipase also increases, but the change in activity of the lipase with concentration of the added vitamin is not much after a concentration of $\times 20$ mg. of the vitamins.

These investigations prove that water-soluble vitamins like ascorbic acid, thiamine and riboflavin accelerate the lipase activity which gives a clue that it may not be necessary to remove these vitamins from lipolytic molds while investigating the separation of lipase from lipolytic molds.

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